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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE**EGAMOVA Malika Tursunovna**

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THE IMPORTANCE OF BLOOD RHEOLOGY IN DIABETES IN THE ORIGIN OF ISCHEMIC STROKE AND THE EFFECT OF HIRUDOTHERAPY ON BLOOD RHEOLOGY

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15008023>**ABSTRACT**

This article examines the effect of diabetes on blood rheology, the origin of ischemic stroke, and the role of hirudotherapy in this process. Blood clotting and circulatory disorders in diabetes increase the risk of many cardiovascular diseases, in particular, ischemic stroke. Hirudotherapy, that is, the use of blood-sucking medical leeches, is considered an effective tool for improving blood rheology and normalizing blood circulation. This article also discusses the negative and positive aspects of the effect of hirudotherapy on blood rheology and the prevention of ischemic stroke. Scientific studies and practical approaches presented in the article are important for reducing the risk of ischemic stroke and treating patients with diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetes, blood rheology, ischemic stroke, hirudotherapy, blood coagulation, blood circulation, health, cardiovascular diseases.

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ РЕОЛОГИИ КРОВИ ПРИ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ В ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИИ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОГО ИНСУЛЬТА И ВЛИЯНИЕ ГИРУДОТЕРАПИИ НА РЕОЛОГИЮ КРОВИ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье рассмотрено влияние сахарного диабета на реологию крови, возникновение ишемического инсульта и роль гирудотерапии в этом процессе. Нарушения свертываемости крови и кровообращения при сахарном диабете повышают риск развития многих сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний, в частности ишемического инсульта. Гирудотерапия, то есть применение кровососущих медицинских пиявок, считается эффективным средством

улучшения реологии крови и нормализации кровообращения. В данной статье также рассматриваются отрицательные и положительные стороны влияния гирудотерапии на реологию крови и профилактику ишемического инсульта. Представленные в статье научные исследования и практические подходы имеют важное значение для снижения риска ишемического инсульта и лечения больных сахарным диабетом.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет, реология крови, ишемический инсульт, гирудотерапия, свертывание крови, кровообращение, здоровье, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания.

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QANDLI DIABETDA QON REALOGIYASINING ISHEMIK INSULT KELIB CHIQUISHIDAGI AHAMIYATI HAMDA GIRUDOTERAPIYANING QON REOLOGIYASIGA TA'SIRI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada qandli diabetning qon reologiyasiga ta'siri, ishemik insultning kelib chiqishi va girudoterapiyaning bu jarayondagi o'rni o'rganiladi. Qandli diabetda qonning qo'yiqlashuvi va qon aylanishining buzilishi ko'plab yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, xususan, ishemik insult xavfini oshiradi. Girudoterapiya, ya'ni qon so'ruvchi tibbiyot zulumlaridan foydalanishga, qon reologiyasini yaxshilash va qon aylanishini normallashtirishda samarali vosita sifatida qaraladi. Ushbu maqolada, shuningdek, girudoterapiyaning qon reologiyasiga ta'siri va ishemik insultni oldini olishdagi salbiy va ijobiy tomonlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada keltirilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar va amaliy yondoshuvlar qandli diabet bilan og'riqan bemorlar uchun ishemik insult xavfini kamaytirish va davolashda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: qandli diabet, qon reologiyasi, ishemik insult, girudoterapiya, qon ivishi, qon aylanishi, sog'liqni saqlash, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklar.

Kirish: Qandli diabet, qand kasalligi- organizmda insulin tanqisligi va moddalar almashinuvi buzilishi natijasida kelib chiqadigan kasallik. Qandli diabet kasalligi sharq xalq tabobat tarixida juda qadimdan ma'lum. Abu Ali ibn Sino bu dardga alohida e'tibor beradi. "Suv qanday ichilgan bo'lsa, shu holda chiqadi", deb yozadi u. Bemorning ko'p suv ichishi boshqa kasalliklarni ham keltirib chiqaradi va bemor juda ozib ketadi. Davolarga to'xtab tabib: "Bemorga sovuq mizojli suyuqliklar ichir, sovuqjomga sol, nordon ayron ichir, mevalar ber, yalpiz damlab ichir, ya'ni bemorni ho'lla, sovut", deydi. Bu - kasallik odam badanida issiqlikning oshib ketishi tufayli paydo bo'lishini bildiradi. Qandli diabet kasalligi tarixiy tibbiy manbalarga ko'ra, nasliy bo'lishi ham mumkin. Qandli diabetda qonda qand moddasi keskin ko'payib, siydik bilan chiqib turadi, tashnalik, ozib ketish, quvvatsizlik, badan qichishishi va boshqalar alomatlar kuzatiladi. [14].

Qandli diabet (QD) — organizmda insulinning yetarli miqdorda ishlab chiqarilmasligi yoki unga nisbatan hujayralarning sezgirligini yo'qotishi bilan xarakterlangan kasallik bo'lib, bu holat nafaqat organizmdagi glyukoza miqdorining oshishiga olib keladi, balki yurak-qon tomir tizimiga ham zarar yetkazadi. QD bemorlarida qon reologiyasi o'zgaradi, bu esa qonning quyushuvi, qon aylanishining sekinlashishi va shu bilan birga ishemik insult xavfini oshiradi. Ishemik insult, miyaga qon yetkazilishining to'xtashi natijasida yuzaga keladigan kasallik bo'lib, unda asab hujayralari o'limi yoki jiddiy shikastlanishi kuzatiladi. [6; 8; 12; 17].

Diabetda qonning reologik xususiyatlari — ya'ni, uning yopishqoqligi, qon tarkibidagi eritrotsitlarning agregatsiyasi va trombozga moyilligi o'zgarib bo'ladi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar, qon aylanishining sekinlashishiga, mikrovaskulyar zararlarga va yurak-qon tomir tizimidagi og'ir patologiyalarga olib keladi. Shu sababli, qandli diabetni samarali boshqarish, uning qon reologiyasiga ta'sirini kamaytirish va ishemik insult xavfini oldini olishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada

qandli diabetda qon reologiyasining o'zgarishlari, ishemik insultning rivojlanishiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi va girudoterapiyaning qon reologiyasiga bo'lgan ijobiy ta'siri o'rganiladi.

Qandli diabetda qon reologiyasi asosan bir qancha omillar ta'sirida o'zgaradi. Bularning eng muhimi qon yopishqoqligi, trombozga moyillik va qon aylanishining buzilishi hisoblanadi. Qandli diabetda qon yopishqoqligi oshadi, bu esa qonning tomirlarda harakatlanishini qiyinlashtiradi va mikrovaskulyar tiqilishlar xavfini oshiradi. Trombozga moyillik ham oshadi, chunki qondagi trombositlar ko'payadi va ularning faoliyati kuchayadi. Bu holat qonning ivishiga olib keladi va ishemik insultning kelib chiqishiga turtki bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, qon aylanishining sekinlashishi, tomirlar elastikligining pasayishi va mikrovaskulyar zararlanishlar, qandli diabetda tez-tez uchraydigan holatlardir. Bu holatlar nafaqat insulinning organizmga tarqalishiga, balki butun yurak-qon tomir tizimining yomonlashishiga sabab bo'ladi. [11; 14].

Girudoterapiya, ya'ni zuluklar yordamida davolash, qadim zamonlardan buyon ishlatilgan bir tibbiy amaliyot bo'lib, qon ivishini kamaytirish va qon aylanishini yaxshilashda samarali vosita sifatida qaraladi. Girudoterapiya qonning yopishqoqligi va trombozga moyillikni kamaytiradi, qon aylanishini normallashtiradi va mikrovaskulyar qon oqimini yaxshilaydi. Bu usul, ayniqsa, qandli diabetdan aziyat chekayotgan bemorlarda, qon reologiyasini yaxshilashga va ishemik insult xavfini kamaytirishga yordam beradi. [5].

Girudoterapiya qon ivishini kamaytirish orqali qon aylanishini yaxshilaydi. Zuluk so'lagining tarkibida girudin deb ataladigan moddalar mavjud bo'lib, ular trombin faoliyatini faol qilib, qon ivish jarayonini to'xtatadi. Bu holat trombositlarning birikishini va tromboz jarayonlarini kamaytiradi, bu esa qonning normal aylanishini ta'minlaydi. Shu bilan birga, girudoterapiya orqali qonning yopishqoqligi kamayib, mikrotomirlarning tiqilib qolish xavfi kamayadi.

Girudoterapiyaning yana bir ijobiy ta'siri, u qon aylanishini yaxshilash orqali mikrovaskulyar qon oqimini tiklaydi. Qandli diabetda mikrovaskulyar qon aylanishining buzilishi tufayli, turli organlar va to'qimalarga qon yetkazib berish qiyinlashadi. Girudoterapiya esa bu jarayonni yaxshilab, mikrovaskulyar qon oqimini normallashtirishga yordam beradi. Bu, o'z navbatida, insult xavfini kamaytirishga yordam beradi. [6; 8; 16; 17].

Shuningdek, girudoterapiya antiagregant va antikoagulyant ta'sir ko'rsatadi, bu esa trombositlar va qon ivish tizimini boshqarishda samarali vosita hisoblanadi. Qon ivishining kamayishi, mikrovaskulyar tiqilishlarning oldini olishga, qonning normal harakatlanishiga va tomirlarning to'siqsiz faoliyat yuritishiga yordam beradi.

Bundan tashqari, girudoterapiya, qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda, yuqori qon bosimi, qonni quyuqlashtiruvchi omillar va mikrovaskulyar zararlarni kamaytirish orqali umumiy salomatlikni yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Girudoterapiya nafaqat qon reologiyasini normallashtiradi, balki qon tomirlarining elastikligini oshiradi va qon aylanishini to'liq tiklashga yordam beradi. Shu tarzda, girudoterapiya qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda ishemik insultni oldini olishda samarali vosita bo'lishi mumkin.

Qandli diabetda qon reologiyasining ishemik insult kelib chiqishidagi ahamiyati: Qandli diabetda qon reologiyasi o'zgarishi asosan quyidagi omillar bilan bog'liq:

1. **Qon yopishqoqligi:** Qandli diabetda qon yopishqoqligi oshadi, bu esa qonning tomirlarda harakatlanishiga qiyinchilik yaratadi. yopishqoqlikning oshishi mikrotomirlarning tiqilib qolishiga olib keladi va bu, o'z navbatida, ishemik insultning kelib chiqish xavfini oshiradi.

2. **Trombozga moyillik:** QD bemorlarida qon ivish tizimi buziladi, qon plazmasida trombozitlar ko'payadi va trombin miqdori oshadi. Bu qonning qotib qolishiga olib keladi va ishemik insultga sabab bo'lishi mumkin.

3. **Qon aylanishining buzilishi:** Qandli diabetda yuqori qon bosimi va qonni quyuqlashtiruvchi omillar ta'sirida, mikrovaskulyar qon aylanishi yomonlashadi, bu esa insulinni yetarli darajada etkazib berishda muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi.

4. **Mikrovaskulyar zararlar:** QD, ayniqsa uzoq muddat davomida boshqarilmasa, arteriyalarda mikrovaskulyar zararlarga olib keladi. Bu tomirlarning elastikligini yo'qotishi, qon aylanishining yomonlashishiga va ishemik insult xavfini oshishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Shu sababli, qandli diabetda ishemik insultning kelib chiqishini oldini olish uchun qon reologiyasini yaxshilash va qonning normal xususiyatlarini tiklash zarurdir.

Girudoterapiyaning qon reologiyasiga ta'siri: Girudoterapiya, ya'ni zuluklar yordamida davolash, qadim zamonlardan buyon ishlatiladigan bir tibbiy amaliyotdir. Ushbu usul, qon ivishini kamaytirish va qon aylanishini yaxshilashda samarali vosita sifatida qaraladi. Girudoterapiya quyidagi yo'llar bilan qon reologiyasini yaxshilashga yordam beradi:

1. **Qon ivishini kamaytirish:** Zuluklar so'lagi, o'zining noyob biokimyoviy tarkibi orqali qonning ivish qobiliyatini bloklaydi va tromb hosil bo'lishining oldini oladi. Bu usul, qonning normal aylanishini ta'minlab, ishemik insult xavfini kamaytiradi.

2. **Qon ivuvchanligini kamaytirishi:** Girudoterapiya qon yopishqoqligini kamayishiga yordam beradi, bu esa qonning to'g'ri va samarali aylanishiga yordam beradi. Natijada, mikrotomirlarda qon oqimining sekinlashuvi va tiqilib qolishi kamayadi.

3. **Antiagregant va antikoagulyant ta'siri:** Girudoterapiya trombositlarning birikishini va trombin faoliyatini faol qilish orqali antiagregant va antikoagulyant ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bu qonning ivishini to'xtatish va tomirlarda qonning to'siqlanishini kamaytirish orqali ishemik insultning oldini olishda muhim o'rin tutadi.

4. **Qon aylanishini yaxshilash:** Girudoterapiya, qonni o'tkazuvchanligini oshirish va mikrovaskulyar qon aylanishini yaxshilash orqali qon aylanishini normallashtiradi, bu esa umumiy salomatlikni yaxshilaydi va ishemik insult xavfini kamaytiradi. [19].

Xulosa: Qandli diabetda qon reologiyasining o'zgarishi va ishemik insultning rivojlanishidagi muhim o'rin ko'rsatilgan. Girudoterapiya, qon ivishini kamaytirish, yopishqoqligi pasaytirish va qon aylanishini yaxshilash orqali ishemik insult xavfini kamaytirishda samarali bo'lishi mumkin. Bu usul, qandli diabetdan aziyat chekayotgan bemorlar uchun qo'shimcha davolash vositasi sifatida muhimdir. Shuningdek, bu maqola, qandli diabetni boshqarishda va ishemik insultni oldini olishda girudoterapiyaning potentsialini taqdim etadi.

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